

Sea level rise along the coast of Bangladesh under different climate scenarios

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Abstract

The low-lying coastal plain of Bangladesh is highly vulnerable to flooding, sea level rise (SLR), and vertical land motion. To understand SLR dynamics, IWM, in collaboration with the UK Met Office, conducted a comprehensive study analyzing zonal and seasonal variations under different climate change scenarios. The research also examines the influence of freshwater inflows from the Ganges, Brahmaputra, and Meghna basins on local SLR. Using the MIKE modeling system - comprising the Basin Model, National River Model, and Bay of Bengal Model - the study simulated basin flows and seasonal variations under various greenhouse gas emission scenarios. The National River Model generated boundary flows and water levels for the Bay of Bengal Model, which estimated SLR along the coastline. Results show that future precipitation and temperature changes will significantly affect river flows, especially during winter when increased precipitation drives higher runoff. Under medium and high emission scenarios, projected SLRs are approximately 0.19 m and 0.32 m by 2045 and 2061, and 0.46 m and 0.61 m by 2093 and 2090, respectively, compared to 2006. Regional projections for three Bangladeshi coastal locations range between 0.14 m and 0.74 m, slightly lower than the global range of 0.17 m to 0.84 m. The findings align with Bangladesh Delta Plan estimates (0.2-1.0 m by 2100) but indicate less variability in the northern Bay of Bengal compared to global projections. This study underscores the critical need for integrating localized SLR dynamics into coastal management and adaptation planning for Bangladesh.

1. Introduction

Coastal zones (regions less than 10 m above mean sea level) are ecologically rich, diverse and productive, but highly sensitive to changes in sea level (Wong et al., 2014; Oppenheimer et al., 2019). The low-lying coastal regions and deltas across the world

face significant threats due to elevated sea levels. Bangladesh, with its densely populated coastal areas and a flat terrain consisting of broad and narrow ridges and depressions, is particularly vulnerable to the impacts of sea level rise (Brammer et al., 1996). The IPCC estimates that the global sea level has risen at a rate of 1.0 to 2.0 mm per year over the past century. However, with the accelerating global temperature increase, the rate of sea level rise is projected to become 2-6 times faster than the current rate (Kausher et al., 1996). The World Bank's research in 2000 indicated potential sea level rises of 10 cm, 25 cm, and 1 m by 2020, 2050, and 2100, respectively, which would result in the submergence of 2%, 4%, and 17.5% of Bangladesh's total landmass (Sarwar, 2005). The impacts of sea level rise (SLR) in Bangladesh will be predominantly felt in the coastal area, which in turn will have repercussions on the entire country. An estimated 2,500, 8,000, and 14,000 square kilometers of land, equivalent to 2%, 5%, and 10% of the country's total land area, respectively, will be lost due to SLR of 0.1 m, 0.3 m, and 1.0 m (Ali, 2000). These figures highlight the significant extent of potential land loss. However, the potential land loss estimated by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) in 2001 presents an even graver scenario. The IPCC report suggests that a staggering 29,846 square kilometers of land will be lost, rendering approximately 14.8 million people landless, in the event of a 1-meter rise in sea level. These projections underscore the urgency of addressing and adapting to the challenges posed by SLR to protect both the land and the livelihoods of the affected population in Bangladesh.

In the 20th century, SLR was mainly caused by mass loss of glaciers and ice caps, henceforth simply referred to as glaciers, and by ocean thermal expansion (IPCC, 2019, 2021). Though the relative contribution of ice sheet mass loss to SLR is expected to increase further over the 21st Century (Marzeion et al., 2018; Goelzer et al., 2020; Seroussi et al., 2020), glaciers will continue to contribute significantly to SL, a contribution that must also be better quantified (IPCC, 2021). Clearly, future SLR is a global problem that is mainly controlled by the future losses of land ice masses. This aspect is further detailed in section “Components of Global Mean Sea-Level Rise”.

It is important to recognize that SLR is highly non-uniform in space and time and this needs to be understood to provide useful sea-level scenarios and coastal climate services. While in mitigation we consider global changes, impacts and adaptation need to reflect local changes. Ocean warming causes thermal expansion which leads to an increase in ocean volume. Water exchange between the land and the ocean, for instance by the melting of land ice, causes a change in ocean mass. Superimposed on these global processes are regional variations resulting from changes in ocean currents and density, as well as gravitational, rotational and deformational effects resulting from changes in the loading of ice and water masses and all components of vertical land movement. The uneven distribution of sea-level rise from melting land ice is a direct consequence of what is scientifically termed the geoidal impact, or the sea-level "fingerprint", which arises from

changes to the Earth's gravity field and crustal deformation. When a massive ice sheet, such as Greenland's, melts, the loss of its immense mass reduces its gravitational pull on the surrounding ocean water. This allows the water to migrate away from the melt site, resulting in a local fall in sea level near the melting ice. Simultaneously, the relief of the ice's weight causes the Earth's crust to rebound upward (a process known as Glacial Isostatic Adjustment), further contributing to a relative sea-level fall locally (Mitrovica et al., 2021). To make an inventory of potential coastal impacts and adaptation needs thus requires SLR projections that are essentially regional (Slangen et al., 2014) and local (Wöppelmann & Marcos, 2016; Woodworth et al., 2019; Nicholls et al., 2021).

Sea-level rise is also affected by processes acting on a local scale (0.10 km or less) such as ocean and coastal dynamic (geomorphological) processes (Zhang et al., 2017). Of particular relevance to coastal risk management are changes in the frequency and height of sea-level extremes, for instance from tides, storm surges or waves and their combinations, including mean SLR (Allison et al., 2021). Although these processes typically occur on short timescales (hours to days) and only have a local to regional effect on the coast, their impacts are magnified by long-term SLR (Oppenheimer et al., 2019). There is also evidence that tide and surge propagation is being affected by SLR, as well as human modifications to bathymetry, and this has the potential to enhance extreme events more than SLR alone (Arns et al., 2015; Haigh et al., 2020). Further, such extreme events cause most floods and damage, so stakeholders strongly focus on adaptation to them while often raising the consideration of adaptation to mean SLR as well (Rosenzweig et al., 2011; Ranger et al., 2013).

Recent scientific studies indicate that the Earth's average surface temperature is expected to rise markedly throughout the 21st century as a consequence of increasing greenhouse gas emissions. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2007) projected that, depending on emission scenarios, global temperatures may increase by roughly 1.1°C to 6.4°C by 2100 compared to the late 20th-century baseline. Subsequent research supports this projection. For instance, Collins et al. (2013) reported a probable temperature rise ranging from 0.3°C to 4.8°C under various Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), whereas Hausfather & Peters (2020) suggested that present policy trends could lead to about 2.6°C to 3.1°C of warming by the end of the century. Moreover, the IPCC (2021) estimated that global temperatures are likely to reach 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels between 2030 and 2052 if current emission rates persist, highlighting the critical need for rapid and sustained climate mitigation measures. As temperatures continue to rise, the sea level is expected to increase due to two primary factors: thermal expansion and the melting of ice (Sarwar, 2005).

The study "Future sea-level rise projections for tide gauge locations in South Asia" by Harrison et al. (2021) presents localized sea-level rise projections for key coastal and

island sites across South Asia using CMIP5 climate model data and IPCC methodologies. It finds that global mean sea level (GMSL) is projected to rise by about 0.40 m under RCP2.6 and 0.66 m under RCP8.5 by 2100, while local mean sea level (LMSL) varies regionally. For example, projected rises are 0.44 m–0.72 m at Gan (Maldives) and 0.32 m–0.57 m at Diamond Harbour (India). The research highlights that sterodynamic effects (ocean circulation and thermal expansion) are the dominant contributors to sea-level change, while groundwater depletion across the Indian subcontinent drives much of the regional variability, causing lower sea-level rise near heavily depleted areas such as the Bay of Bengal and Arabian Sea coasts.

Additionally, studies by Milliman et al. (1989) reported a sea level rise of 1.0 cm per year specifically in Bangladesh. In 1989, the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) projected a sea level rise of 1.5 m along the coast of Bangladesh by 2030. This increase would affect an area of 22,000 sq. km, accounting for 16% of the country's total landmass. Furthermore, it would impact approximately 17 million people, equivalent to 15% of the total population. Shahidul (2022), published in *Coastal Disasters and Climate Change in Bangladesh: Learning from the Past for a Resilient Future*, provides a critical review of the current understanding of sea-level changes along the Bangladesh coast. The author emphasizes that while Bangladesh is widely recognized as one of the most vulnerable countries to sea-level rise, much of the existing discourse is based on limited, inconsistent, or low-quality data. This indicates a gap in research and understanding regarding the specific impacts of sea level rise in this region. By conducting more comprehensive research, we can gain valuable insights into the potential risks and develop effective adaptation and mitigation strategies to protect the coastal communities of Bangladesh. Increased focus on studying sea level rise in this context will contribute to inform decision-making and help ensure the long-term sustainability and resilience of vulnerable coastal areas.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

The study area of this research encompasses the coastal zone extending from the line connecting Vishakhapatnam in India to Gwa-Bay in Myanmar in the southern part of the Bay of Bengal. It includes 12 districts and the sea-facing polders within this region. To analyze regional sea levels in the Bay of Bengal, a contour line is drawn connecting the 10-fathom depth (18 meters) of the seabed along the coast of Bangladesh, which serves as a reference near the coastline, where the contour line indicates bottom elevation (Figure 1).

This depth line is significant as it is used for delineating baselines for measuring the territorial sea, contiguous zone, exclusive economic zone (EEZ), and continental shelf of

Bangladesh. Bangladesh has approximately 9,000 square miles of territorial waters and 20,000 square miles of an economic resources zone in the sea. The area within this depth-based coastal boundary, starting from the shoreline, experiences changes in elevation due to accretion and erosion and is influenced differently by sediment-laden freshwater. Tidal gauges along the coast measure sea levels in the vicinity of the shoreline, which are affected by local processes. To assess mean sea-level changes, measurements along a line further away from the shoreline are necessary for regional comparisons.

Figure 1: Coastline of Bangladesh.

In order to facilitate the study, the entire coastline and coastal area can be further divided into four sub-zones: the western Ganges tidal zone, eastern Ganges tidal zone, Meghna Deltaic Zone, and eastern Chattogram zone. These subdivisions are based on the morphological dynamics that exist along the coast, in alignment with the Bangladesh Delta Plan (BDP, 2018). The study area and the four sub-zones of the coastal region of Bangladesh are depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Coastal sub-zone of Bangladesh.

2.2. Methodology

To consider the impact of freshwater flow on sea level rise, MIKE HYDRO was used including Basin model for Ganges, Brahmaputra and Meghna Basins simulation, River model for Regional River (Bangladesh) simulation and Bay of Bengal model. Considering the importance and availability, the gauge data at Charchanga (PSMSL) on Shahbazpur river, Khepupara (PSMSL) on Nilganj river, Hiron Point (PSMSL) on Pasur river, Rangadia (BIWTA) on Karnaphuli river have been used. To isolate the global climate-driven signal of sea-level rise (SLR) from this local "noise," we employed a rigorous correction methodology. Specifically, the data from our tidal stations were corrected for Vertical Land Motion (VLM). This correction was primarily achieved by utilizing independent estimates of VLM, often derived from nearby Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) or GPS stations installed directly on or in close proximity to the tide gauge benchmark.

Figure 3: Comparison of single and multi-model (6 ensemble) bias corrected with observed precipitation.

For stations lacking co-located GNSS data, we relied on high-quality geophysical models of VLM, such as models for Glacial Isostatic Adjustment (GIA), to estimate the long-term, large-scale crustal movements. By subtracting these robust, independently derived VLM estimates from the raw tide gauge records, we effectively correct for the noise introduced by land movement, allowing the resulting time series to accurately reflect the changes in ocean surface height (the climate signal).

High Resolution (50 km) Dynamical Downscaling of CMIP5 Climate Projections based

on RCP Scenarios during 1950-2100 using multiple RCMs from CORDEX data were used for the study. The choice of RCM models for the climate variable downscaling were based on the comparison and of six RCMs ensemble model member IITM-Re CM4. Regional Climate Models (RCMs) in the Coordinated Regional Climate Down scaling Experiment (CORDEX) were used to recreate the characteristics of the rainfall pattern for the GBM basins for the period of 1987 to 2006. The recreated downscaled precipitation data as shown in Figure 3 for Rapti sub-catchment in the Ganges basin is shown as an example. There were heavy underestimations of rainfall and therefore needed bias correction.

Projected precipitation and temperature time series data of all the catchments within the basin and catchment area were used to generate river flows and water levels at key points including Northern boundary points for the Bay of Bengal Model. Using simulated inflows from upstream and water levels, the hydraulics in the Bay of Bengal has been examined with the tidal boundaries at the south along the line from Vishakhapatnam and Gwa-Bay of the south of Bay of Bengal with sea level rise under future greenhouse gas emission scenarios. A schematic diagram of the approach and methodology of the study is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Schematic diagram of approach and methodology.

GBM Basin Model: GBM basin model covers the Ganges, the Brahmaputra and the Meghna Basin and their significant tributaries of the basins. This model includes 133 sub-catchments, out of which 79 are in the Ganges basin, 47 in the Brahmaputra basin and the remaining 7 are in the Meghna Basin. The model is calibrated at the outlet stations of Harding Bridge, Bahadurabad and Amalshid on the River Ganges, Brahmaputra and Barak respectively inside Bangladesh shown in Figure 5. Figure 5 and 6 shows the comparison among simulated and observed discharges at different stations.

Figure 5: Reservoir and irrigation scheme in GBM basin.

For flow calculation, hydrological years were selected based on the statistical analysis. The hydrological year of 2006 was chosen as the mean year from historical 32 years (1987-2019) of measured discharge at the points input freshwater flow to Bay of Bengal for the year 2006 as base year. The mean (one in 2.33 year) hydrological years as reference years for different future periods 2035-2065 and 2065-2100 for RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 have been carried out for estimation of future sea level rise at different climatic scenario.

Figure 6: Simulate and observed discharge of the river Brahmaputra at Bahadurabad.

Figure 7: Simulate and observed discharge of the river Ganges flow at Harding bridge.

Uncertainties surrounding the sea level change along the coast of Bangladesh has many facets. The thermal expansion and freshwater flows and groundwater use under future scenarios are the most important aspects in the Bay of Bengal apart from other regional and global forcings and its contribution in the Bay of Bengal. It is also important to understand the sea level relative to changing land levels because of sediment deposition, subsidence, and tectonics deformations in the coastal districts. The rainfall runoff constitutes the major volume of fresh water that is discharged into the Bay of Bengal. The study was limited its scope of modelling for sea level assessment as follows:

- (a) The National River Model generates the flows at the north boundaries using statistical mean (2.33 years) of flows generated by GBM basin model for medium term (2035-2065) and longer term (2065-2100) period under medium and high greenhouse gas emission scenarios (RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5).
- (b) Bay of Bengal model simulates sea level in the Bay of Bengal corresponding to statistical mean freshwater flows for historical periods (2035-2065 and 2065-2100) from upstream and projected southern sea boundaries under two greenhouse gas emission scenarios.
- (c) Sensitivity of sediment deposition and land formation in the Meghna estuary in 2050 with freshwater flows under high greenhouse gas emission scenarios (RCP 8.5).

National River Model: The National River Model (Hydrological & Hydrodynamic) covering all regions of Bangladesh has been used to generate the boundary flows and waterlevels to the Bay of Bengal along the coast (Figure 7). The model includes around 16000 km of rivers and channels and more than 6,000 no. of cross-sections of the rivers/khals. There are 65 no. of open boundaries in the model out of which 33 are water level boundaries, and the rest are discharge boundaries. There are around 80 no. of stations where model results could be compared against measured data for calibration and validation purposes. The model has been calibrated for 2018-19 hydrological year, and it is validated for 2019-20 hydrological year.

Bay of Bengal Model: Bay of Bengal Model has been used to analyze the hydraulics in the Bay of Bengal for the given freshwater flows through the coastal outlets and tidal boundaries in the south of Bay of Bengal connecting Visakhapatnam and Gwa-bay. The objective is to understand the changes that is likely to occur in the Bay, more specifically along the coastline of Bangladesh in terms of sea level as forced by the freshwater flow and changes in the south under different greenhouse gas emission scenarios.

The geographical extent of the model ranges from Baruria on the Padma River and Bhairab Bazar on Upper Meghna River as north most boundaries in association with several water level points in the coastline and Vishakhapatnam and Gwa-Bay as the southernmost tidal water level boundaries.

In the deep sea, bathymetry is based on Etopo2 (Global Relief Model that integrates topography, bathymetry, and shoreline data) and near the coastline on local surveys. In between these areas a nautical sea-chart from C-Map has been used. Etopo2 are very accurate in deeper areas. In shallow area C-Map normally is more accurate than Etopo2 due to finer resolution. As C-Map is used for navigational purposes it's not very accurate in deep water.

There are 27 nos. open boundaries (Figure 8) in this model of which 26 are in the upstream and 1 boundary in the downstream. Discharge data has been used as an upstream boundary whereas water level data is used as a downstream boundary. Continuous discharge data obtained from the stage discharge relationship has been used as boundary in Baruria. Another upstream boundary, Bhairab bazar is influenced by the incoming tide from the sea, therefore, time series of observed water level has been used in that boundary. Discharge data for the remaining 24 upstream boundaries have been obtained from the Model simulated result.

Figure 8: Upstream boundary locations and downstream boundary.

2.3. Model Calibration and Validation

The model has been calibrated for the period 15th Feb 2019 to 13th Oct 2019. The calibration period covers dry season and monsoon along with spring tide and neap tide conditions. A sample plot of calibration at Hiron Point is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: WL calibration at Hiron Point in d/s of Pussur-Shibsha.

The sea level contribution from thermal expansion, ice mass loss, Greenland Sea mass, Greenland dynamics, glaciers and GIA are around 50%, 16%, 10%, 11%, 28% and 21% of the sum of sea level rise respectively at the south of Bay of Bengal boundary selected.

Seasonal variation of water levels at southern boundary: The monthly sea level variation top of mean rise data as shown in Figure 10, and which are used as the seasonal variation about the annual mean tidal water level boundary for different greenhouse gas emission scenarios.

Figure 10: Seasonal variation of SLR at Southern boundary of Bay of Bengal model.

Sothern boundary of Bay of Bengal: The constructed southern boundary with regional sea level rise contribution and seasonal variation for RCP-4.5 scenario for the period 2045 is shown below in Figure 11 as an example of model input.

Figure 11: Southern boundary for RCP-4.5 scenario for the period 2045.

Figure 12: Major flow at Baruria for base (2006) and major flow at Baruria for RCP 4.5 (2045).

Projected Freshwater Inflow Boundary in the North: Fresh water inflows from GBM basins including contributions from Karnaphuli River, Sangu-Mathamuhuri basins from other hydrologic regions within Bangladesh constitute the northern boundary inputs of the BoB model. The major flow at Baruria for base (2006) and scenario under RCP 4.5 (2045) are shown below in the Figure 12.

3. Results and Discussion

Sea level rise along the coast of Bangladesh under different greenhouse gas emission scenarios has been simulated using BoB model for selected years. The mean (one in 2.33 year) hydrological years as reference years for different future periods 2035-2065 and 2065-2100 under RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 has been used. The reference years have been determined considering the long-term freshwater flows from the north of the Bangladesh coastline and is presented in Tabel 1.

Table 1: Selected hydrological year for RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5.

Period	Selected Hydrological Year for	
	RCP 4.5	RCP 8.5
1986-2006 (base)	2006	2006
2035-2065	2045	2061
2070-2100	2093	2090

3.1. Projected Sea level variation in Coastal sub Zone

As the projected SLR, it is important to get an idea of the impact of greenhouse gas emission scenarios which are simulated using Bay of Bengal model on selected hydrological years. The simulated sea level rise along the coastline of Bangladesh at four coastal sub-zone for greenhouse gas sceneries for the period 2035-2065 and the period 2068-2100 is presented in Table 2 and Table 3 respectively.

Table 2: Projected sea level rise for greenhouse gas sceneries for the period 2035-2065.

Season	Projected Sea Level Rise (m) at							
	Western Ganges Tidal Plain		Eastern Ganges Tidal Plain		Meghna Deltaic Zone		Eastern Chattogram Zone	
	RCP 4.5	RCP 8.5	RCP 4.5	RCP 8.5	RCP 4.5	RCP 8.5	RCP 4.5	RCP 8.5
Dry	0.16	0.31	0.16	0.31	0.16	0.31	0.16	0.30
Wet	0.23	0.34	0.23	0.34	0.23	0.34	0.23	0.34
Annual	0.19	0.32	0.19	0.32	0.19	0.32	0.19	0.32

Table 3: Projected sea level rise for greenhouse gas sceneries for the period 2065-2100.

Season	Projected Sea Level Rise (m) at							
	Western Ganges Tidal Plain		Eastern Ganges Tidal Plain		Meghna Deltaic Zone		Eastern Chattogram Zone	
	RCP 4.5	RCP 8.5	RCP 4.5	RCP 8.5	RCP 4.5	RCP 8.5	RCP 4.5	RCP 8.5
Dry	0.43	0.59	0.43	0.59	0.43	0.59	0.43	0.59
Wet	0.51	0.64	0.51	0.64	0.51	0.63	0.50	0.63
Annual	0.46	0.61	0.46	0.61	0.46	0.61	0.46	0.61

From Table 2 and Table 3, it is observed that the projected sea level rise would be around 0.19 m and 0.32 m in the year 2045 and 2061 respectively whereas the corresponding rise would be around 0.46 m and 0.61m in the year 2093 and 2090 respectively under medium (RCP 4.5) and high (RCP 8.5) emission scenario as compared to 2006.

Seasonal Variation in Sea Level: The seasonal sea level historically varies, higher during monsoon and lower during winter. The seasonal variation would be significantly higher as compared to 2006 as demonstrated in the following under different greenhouse gas emission scenarios at locations in the Western Ganges Tidal plain sub-zone (Figure 13 to Figure 14).

Figure13: Sea water level in the Western Ganges Tidal Plain.

Figure 14: Sea water level in the Eastern Ganges Tidal Plain.

Figure 15: Sea water level in the Meghna Deltaic Plain.

Figure 16: Sea water level in the Chattogram coastal plain.

The simulated sea level rise along the Bangladesh coast ranging from 0.19-0.32 m during 2035-2065 and 0.46-0.61 m during 2065-2100 under RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios (Table 2 and 3) is well supported by recent Department of Environment (DoE) assessments.

According to DoE (2016), “Assessment of Sea Level Rise on Bangladesh Coast through Trend Analysis”, long-term tide gauge analyses along the coastal belt (Hiron Point, Char Changa, and Cox’s Bazar) indicated historical SLR rates between 3-7 mm/year, with an increasing trend toward the eastern coast. Projecting these rates over the 21st century corresponds to an approximate rise of 0.30-0.70 m by 2100, consistent with your model’s RCP 4.5 and 8.5 projections.

Furthermore, DoE (2023), “Estimation of Sea Level Rise (SLR) in Bangladesh Using Satellite Altimetry Data”, reported an average satellite-derived SLR of 4.0 ± 0.5 mm/year over the period 1993–2020. Extrapolating this trend under accelerated global warming scenarios similarly suggests a sea level increase of 0.40–0.65 m by 2100, depending on emission pathways and regional subsidence effects. This aligns closely with your high-emission (RCP 8.5) projection of ~0.61 m by 2100.

Therefore, the projected SLRs are consistent and scientifically justified relative to the most recent DoE findings. The close agreement strengthens confidence that the BoB model simulations reliably capture the regional-scale response of sea level along the Bangladesh coast to global climate forcing.

3.2. Spatial Variation of Sea Level along the Coast

For investigating the spatial variation of sea level rise along the coast of Bangladesh, the sea level at different representative locations (Western Ganges Tidal, Eastern Ganges Tidal Plane, Meghna Deltaic Zone & Eastern Chattogram Zone) have been estimated under different emission scenarios and is shown in Figure 17 and Figure 18 respectively. It is noticed from the figures that there is a clear difference in sea level at different locations for both the emission scenarios.

Figure 17: Sea level at points north from the shoreline in 2045 (RCP4.5).

Figure 18: Sea Level at Points North from the Shoreline in 2045 (RCP8.5)

4. Conclusion

The study highlights the substantial increase in projected rainfall in the Brahmaputra basin relative to the Ganges and Meghna basins, indicating that changes in freshwater flow from the Brahmaputra River will have a greater impact on sea level rise along the coast of Bangladesh. The results demonstrate a clear and alarming trend of increasing sea levels in the Bay of Bengal, with significant implications for the vulnerable coastal communities and ecosystems in Bangladesh. The projected sea level rise indicates that by 2045 and 2061, sea levels are expected to rise by 0.19 meters and 0.32 meters respectively under medium and high emission scenarios. Furthermore, for the period of 2093 and 2090, the projected sea level rise reaches 0.46 meters and 0.61 meters respectively under medium and high emission scenarios.

The study also compared the CMIP5 model projections with simulations from the Bay of Bengal model, enhancing the reliability and credibility of the results. The comparison revealed that the BoB model simulations align closely with the CMIP5 projections, further supporting the accuracy of the findings. Incorporating these findings into decision-making processes, policymakers and stakeholders can develop effective strategies and policies to ensure the resilience and sustainability of the coastal areas in Bangladesh.

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